

EFFECT OF SEEDING FUNGICIDES ON POTATO YIELD

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Abstract. *Phytophthora, alternaria, rhizactonia and fusarium are among the diseases that cause great economic damage to potato farms. If on average 30% of the crop is lost due to these diseases, the amount of waste increases by 5-20% due to rotting in the tubers during storage. The infection in the tubers causes the seedlings to dry up when planted in the soil, and the yield decreases. Thus, the idea of protection from harmful microorganisms, especially from disease-causing fungi, which negatively affect the quantity and quality of the potato crop, is an urgent issue.*

Keywords: *diseases, seeding agents, fungus, bacteria, suspension, trace elements.*

Introduction. By rationally using the available resources and opportunities in our country, guaranteeing the population with agricultural products, further increasing productivity and interest, introducing scientific achievements and modern approaches to the field are urgent issues.

The article provides extensive scientific and practical information on the most advanced practices in protecting agricultural crops, obtaining high-quality products from potatoes among vegetable crops, and protecting against diseases.

In recent years, comprehensive measures have been implemented in our republic in order to fully satisfy the population's needs for food and other agricultural products, especially vegetables. For this purpose, in order to improve the quality of vegetable crops and prevent diseases, it is a good practice to treat seeds with seeders before planting in the following years.

Fertilizers have different effects on plant growth depending on their composition and chemical properties. Some of them contain trace elements necessary for plant growth, while other preparations are used to fight diseases and pests, which can contribute to the growth, development and productivity of plants.

Preparations containing trace elements also have a positive effect on plant growth. For example: micronutrients such as iron, copper and zinc have been found to have a positive effect on the quality and quantity of plant yield.

The drugs used in the fight against diseases and pests also affect the growth of plants. Pest control helps to keep plants healthy and increase productivity. But some drugs, such as herbicides and pesticides, can have a negative effect on plant growth if used in excess. A large number of preparations are toxic to the plant and can destroy the beneficial microflora in the soil, reduce the quality and quantity of the crop.

Medicines used against plant diseases are called fungicides. It is known that disease-causing bacteria and fungi are mainly spread from the air by wind, rain, and insects due to people. If it is applied to the plant, the mouth, smallpox, eye and mechanical injuries will disappear. Some parasites can pass through the epidermis. For example, pathogens of powdery mildew. As soon as it enters the body, its spores turn blue, tear the epidermis, enter the tissue and start feeding. The fungus begins to develop as an exo-parasite (on the plant). In most cases, the parasite cells, tissue

(endoparasite) cyst, cancer, false flour-dew. In such cases, parasites can be lost. That is why it is necessary to pay more attention to preventive measures.

There are currently many types of seed drills known throughout our country. Several types of biological and chemical fertilizers are used to increase potato yield and prevent diseases.

Trichodermin is a biological agent for protecting plants from fungal and bacterial diseases. Trichodermin consists of spores of the soil fungus *Trichoderma lignorum* (at least 2 billion spores per 1 g) and ground grain substrate. Trichodermin is able to suppress more than 60 soil pathogens that cause root and fruit rot, seed infections, macrosporiosis, *Fusarium*, rhizoctonia, phytophthora and other diseases. Trichodermin improves soil fertility, increases seed germination. The drug is used in the form of an aqueous solution. To moisten the seeds, 10 g of trichodermin suspension is prepared for 1 liter of water in which the seeds are stored. For watering plants, trichodermin is diluted with 10 g/l, watered under the roots, but not more than normal watering. For spraying, 10 g is diluted for 5 liters of water.

Maxim XL 035 s.k. has a contact and systemic effect due to the presence of two highly active substances. Fludioxonil-contact-translaminal fungicide of the phenylpyrrole class causes a violation of the osmotic pressure in the fungal cell. Controls economically important diseases caused by fungi of the ascomycete, basidiomycete and poorly developed fungal classes.

A systemic fungicide of the class of mefenoxam-phenylamides disrupts the biosynthesis of nucleic acids (in particular, the activity of RNA polymerase), the synthesis of ribosomal RNA, which leads to the cessation of the division of fungal cells, controls diseases of economic importance caused by fungi of the Oomycete class.

Maksim XL 035 S. K. enhances the germination of seeds, improves the absorption of nutrients and the process of photosynthesis. The drug is a strong immunomodulator and acts as an elicitor - it increases the protective properties of the plant.

Vitavaks 200 FF is a fungicidal fertilizer for pre-planting treatment of grain crops, corn, potatoes from seed mold, root rot and other dangerous diseases.

Carboxin is a compound with structural properties. Carboxin's scope of action is mainly limited to fungi of the basidiomycete class. It is a specific inhibitor of succinic acid oxidation. As a result of binding of the enzyme to carboxin, the flow of electrons through complex II is blocked, which leads to a decrease in the formation of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) and the inhibition of the entire cycle of tricarboxylic acids (Krebs cycle).

The drug effectively suppresses root rot and seed mold, improves the emergence of seedlings and the development of the root system, helps to obtain uniform shoots, and increases the yield potential. Carboxin stops internal infection after 7-8 days, Thiram stops the growth of external and soil infections within 48 hours.

Fulvogumat "Ivan Ovsinsky" is complete growth stimulator, low molecular weight fertilizer. This modification of Fulvogumate with the addition of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and boron is necessary for the full growth and development of plants, participates in protein and carbohydrate metabolism, increases the efficiency of the photosynthesis process, promotes the movement and accumulation of carbohydrates, starch, sucrose. It also increases resistance to diseases, increases yield up to 50% in soils of different fertility levels, creates the best starting conditions for plants, forms a strong root system, allows the plant to produce as many fruits as possible, shortens the ripening time, strengthens general immunity, has an anti-stress effect with negative climatic factors.

Serenada ACO is a *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* qst-713 strain that acts as a root colonizer, creates a physical barrier against soil pathogens, and promotes plant nutrient uptake.

Fungicide Serenada ACO is designed to protect crops from various fungal and bacterial diseases.

It is also effective against many fungal diseases such as phytophthora, *Alternaria*, gray rot, peronosporosis, anthracnose, powdery rot, bacterial diseases such as mucous bacteriosis, vascular bacteriosis, black bacterial spot and bacterial burn.

Research methods: common phytopathological methods were used in the research. N.A. Naumov, A.A. Yachevsky, M.I. Herbariums seeds collected from different varieties of regionalized potatoes were subjected to phytosanitary control, and their phytoexpertise was carried out using the classic methods of Dementeva.

In order to determine the disease of lawns grown from seeds, healthy seedlings, diseased and withered seedlings were counted separately on 1 m². Such sites made up 10% of the studied fields.

In mycological studies, the method of seeding in moist chambers and potato agar medium was used to isolate disease-causing fungi from infected parts of the plant.

Results of the research: In the conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, future potatoes are planted in March, in the southern districts even in late autumn (October-November), at the end of May - June. Potato rows are softened several times during the growing season. Regionalized varieties include: Santa, Dosim Palak, Kizil Koz, Russia.

In order to prevent potato diseases, planting with biological and chemical fungicides before planting is one of the most effective methods. For this purpose, the Russian potato variety was planted with chemical seeders 5-10 days before sowing with biological seeders.

Table 1

Seeders used in the processing of potato seeds

Drug, manufacturing company, country, re-registration date	Consumption rate, ha/kg or ga/l	Which diseases used against	Composition	1 tuber taken from the root plant, gr	Damage %
VITAVAKS 200 FF 34% s.sus.k. (170 g/l + 170 g/l) "Arysta Life Science Great Britain Ltd", Great Britain, 31.12.2024	2,0-2,5	Fuzarioz, root cherish, rizaktonioz	carboxin + thiram	895,0	10,5

MAKSIM XL 035 FS,3,5% sus.k. (25 + 10 g/l) (B) " Syngenta Agro AG", Swizerland, 31.12.2024	5	Alternarioz, fuzarioz, root rot	fludioxonil	885,0	11,3
Fulvogumat Ivan Ovsinsky 4-6% s.e. (titer 2.4 billion/ml) "Zara trust" LLC, Uzbekistan 30.04.2026	5	The aim is to reduce the infection pressure of fusarium and wilt pathogens in plants and soil	Follic acid + humic acid Trichoderma Lignorum (T/viride)	875,0	11,6
SERENADA ACO sus.k. titer at least 1x10 ⁹ KOE/ml « Bayer AG», Germany 31.12.2023	8	Fitoftoroz, alternarioz	Bacillus amylolique faciens shtamm QST-713	900,0	8,4
TRIXODERMIN n.kuk. 6x10 ⁹ kl/ml ISIPQPUz, Uzbekistan 31.12.2023	0,2 kg /t + 0,3 kg/ga	Fuzarioz wither, fitoftoroz	Trichoderma viride H13	935,0	7,8
Control	-	-	-	805,0	16,3

Part of the results: The Russian variety of potatoes was planted with Trichodermin, Serenada ACO, Fulvogumat Ivan Ovsinsky, Maksim XL, Vitavaks seeders. As a result of the study, damage to the potato parts planted with Trichodermin seeding agent was 7.8%, the number of nodules from 1 root potato was 11-14 pieces, weight - 935.0g, damage to potato parts treated with Serenada ACO seeding agent was 8.4 %, the number of nodules obtained from 1 root potato is 10-13 pieces, weight - 900.0 g, damage to potato parts planted with Fulvogumat Ivan Ovsinsky seeder was 11.6%, the number of nodules obtained from 1 root potato was 10-12 pieces, weight - 935.0g, damage in potato parts planted with Maxim XL seeder was 11.3%, the number of nodules from 1 root potato was 8-10, weight - 885.0g, damage in potato parts planted with Vitavaks seeder was 10.5%, the number of nodules from 1 root potato was 8-10 pieces, weight - 895.0.0g. (Table 1)

According to the results of the conducted monitoring, Trichodermin, Serenada aco sus.k. seeders are more effective than other seeders.

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